

MINORITIES' RIGHTS, ESTABLISHMENT, ADMINISTRATION TO RUN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: *The most crucial tool for bringing about social and economic change is education. Since educated and skilled individuals stand to gain the most from the employment opportunities that growth will bring, a population that is well-educated and sufficiently knowledgeable and skilled is not only necessary to support economic growth but also a prerequisite for growth to be inclusive, as per the Twelfth Five-Year Plan, Paragraph 10.1. To fully realise India's human resource potential with justice and excellence, the Ministry of Education is concentrating on an inclusive agenda. The government is dedicated to addressing all minorities' educational deficiencies. In this article, we have discussed the three most crucial elements for minority communities to manage educational institutions: rights, establishment, and administration. According to the Indian constitution, minority institutions are entitled to all national rights. Due to the excellent infrastructure, the legislative jurisdiction also provided these facilities in order to help our country's economic, social, cultural, and general growth and development, as well as to prepare the next generation for a competitive world. NCMEI approved 14147 institutions as minority communities in July 2025. Among the six minorities, Christians make up many of the educational institutions (7862), followed by Muslims (5308), and Parsis (15). Among these, the state of Odisha filed numerous cases. In 2024, there were 1499 pension claims made against Christian minority self-financing educational institutions. In the Indian judiciary, 8250 cases were heard between 1968 and 2025. The High Court of Odisha has upheld these rights in a single ruling that addressed 181 cases and disclosed the petitioner's demand without pension. out of 19 rulings issued by the Indian Supreme Court that might support minority institutions. A significant amount of money was spent by each minority institution to have its rights validated by the relevant authorities. To prevent future needless jurisdictional expenses, it is advised that all jurisdictional authorities maintain, implement, and enforce the rules to be followed by the state authorities. Institutions' establishment roleplay for the entire community, predominantly serves the interests of the minority community or the sole betterment of the minority community. The minority community should determine the selection, removal criteria, and procedures for hiring teaching, administrative staff, and other personnel. The authority to hire and fire staff must come from the minority community. Further, even if teaching or administrative staff may include non-minority persons, judgment has been ordered by the Supreme Court of India, Civil Appellate, original jurisdiction of civil appeal 2286 of 2006 for 11 cases in one direction.*

Keywords: education, Institutions, minorities, Christian, Muslim, appointing, pension, self-financing,

1. INTRODUCTION:

Education has always held a special place in minority protection [70]. The Indian Constitution addresses minorities' rights to create and run educational institutions in Article 30. It gives minorities in language and religion the autonomy to establish and run their educational establishments. Choosing the kind of institution, its administration, and its management are all included in this. The goal of Article 30 is to guarantee minority communities' access to high-quality education while preserving their distinctive cultural and educational identities. The "management quota" is the term used to describe the percentage of seats reserved for students selected by the minority institution when it comes to management. The university does this to make sure that admitted students share its values and advance its academic objectives. The right to create and run their educational institutions is granted to minorities by Article 30 of the Indian Constitution. Preserving the cultural and educational rights of linguistic and religious minorities is the goal of this clause.

Given the importance of education and its necessity, the Constitution included provisions that allow minorities to create and run their educational institutions, as per Article 30, where they can assist students from their community in receiving educational support and privileges.

1.1. Meaning of Minority Institution: Our constitution doesn't define the term "minority," which comes from the Latin word minor and the suffix "ity," which means "in small numbers." In reference to the Kerala education bill, the Supreme Court said that although it was not difficult to assert that a minority refers to a community that is less than half of the total population, it isn't in reference to the entire law. If it is state legislation, the number of residents or citizens in the state would be used to calculate the minority. According to Articles 29 and 30, a state's population would determine its minority status. Regarding the Kerala education bill, it was decided that Christians, Muslims, and Anglo Indians would be considered minorities in Kerala.

The definition of linguistic minority under Article 30 (1) requires that the group have a distinct spoken language and a language without a unique script. All the languages spoken in India lack a unique script. However, the people still speak to them. To safeguard them, Article 30 (1) was added to the Indian Constitution. It is necessary to evaluate a linguistic minority based on the language they speak, not the language they wish their children to learn, and for their future, it will be mandatory to require.

The term "religious minority" refers to a group of people who primarily adhere to one of the many different religions, rather than a particular branch, language, or aspect of it. In the Union Territory of Delhi, Jains and Sikhs have been ruled to be considered religious minorities under Article 30 (1). According to the National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions Act of 2004, a minority is a community as defined by the federal government, and a minority institution is an educational establishment and management that is run by members of the minority.

1.2. Secularism and Non-Secularism: Secularism, a fundamental aspect of the Constitution, must therefore be interpreted in light of Article 30(1), which grants minorities the authority to create and run educational institutions. In 1962, Jamia became a designated university, and in December 1988, a special act of Parliament made it a central university. It was accorded "minority status" by NCMEI in 2011. "Jamia was founded by the Muslims for the benefit of Muslims, and it never lost its identity as a Muslim minority educational institution," according to NCMEI, which meant that it was "covered under Article 30(1), read with Section 2(g) of the National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions Act" (Chisti 2016) [4].

Secular and non-secular states coexist in South Asia. With no official state religion and equal respect for all religions, India is a secular state. In contrast, Pakistan is a non-secular state where Islam is the national religion, and religious leaders have a say in how things are run. Despite being secular at first, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka have been moving in recent years to emphasize religious identities. India's preamble declared the country to be secular when the Forty-second Amendment to the Indian Constitution was passed in 1976. Nonetheless, the Supreme Court of India affirmed that India has been secular from the republic's founding in the 1994 decision of *S. R. Bommai v. Union of India*[1].

1.3. Articles 29 & 30: Articles 29 and 30, which refer to the cultural and educational rights. Article 29 inter alia provides that no citizen will be denied admission to an educational institution maintained wholly or partly from State funds on the grounds only of religion, etc. Article 30 permits all minorities, whether based on religion or language, to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice and further prohibits the State from discriminating against such institutions in the matter of granting. These fundamental rights enshrined in Articles 15, 16, and 25 to 30 leave no manner of doubt that they form part of the basic structure of the Constitution. Besides, by the 42nd Amendment, Part IV-A entitled

'Fundamental Duties' was introduced which inter alia casts a duty on every citizen to cherish and follow the noble ideals which inspired our national struggle for freedom, to uphold and protect the sovereignty, unity and integrity of India, to promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India transcending religious, linguistic and regional or sectional diversities, and to value and preserve the rich heritage of our composite culture. These provisions, which I have recalled briefly, clearly bring out the dual concept of secularism and democracy, the principles of accommodation and tolerance as advocated by Gandhiji and other national leaders. I am, therefore, in agreement with the views expressed by my learned colleagues Sawant, Ramaswamy, and Reddy, JJ., that secularism is a basic feature of our Constitution [2]. They have elaborately dealt with this aspect of the matter, and I can do no better than express my concurrence, but I have said these few words merely to complement their views by pointing out how this concept was understood immediately before the Constitution and till the 42nd Amendment. By the 42nd Amendment, what was implicit was made explicit. 30 After the demise of Gandhiji, national leaders like Pandit Nehru (1946) [5], Maulana Azad, Dr Ambedkar, and others tried their best to see that the secular character of the nation, as bequeathed by Gandhiji, was not jeopardised. Dr Ambedkar, Chairman of the Drafting Committee, aware of the undercurrents, cautioned that India was not yet a consolidated and integrated nation but had to become one. This anxiety was also reflected in his speeches in the Constituent Assembly. He was, therefore, careful while drafting the Constitution to ensure that adequate safeguards were provided in the Constitution to protect the secular character of the country and to keep divisive forces in check so that the interests of religious, linguistic, and ethnic groups were not prejudiced. He carefully weaved Gandhiji's concept of secularism and democracy into the constitutional fabric. This becomes evident from a cursory look at the provisions of the Constitution referred to earlier.

1.4. Preserving the rights of Minorities – Article 29: Every group of Indian people who live on Indian soil and have their unique script, language, and culture must be able to preserve them. The Indian Constitution's Article 29 addresses the protection of minorities' rights, particularly the preservation of their unique language, script, or culture, and the prohibition of discrimination in educational settings. Religion, race, caste, language, or any combination of these should not be grounds for denying a citizen admission to any state-run educational institution or for denying them aid or support from state money. It highlights minority groups' rights to preserve their distinct cultural identities and forbids exclusion from educational institutions on the grounds of caste, language, religion, or ethnicity.

1.5. Freedom to establish or create, administer, and Run Educational Institutions Article -30: The freedom to establish and run educational institutions as they see fit should belong to all minorities. The government must remember that a defined price must be agreed upon in a way that does not violate the rights of minorities if it is purchasing any property from a minority educational institution. The state is not allowed to discriminate against any educational institution based on its minority management, whether that discrimination is based on language or religion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Saima Saeed (2016)[6]: The Aligarh Muslim University's minority status is a confidential matter, but the Indian government shouldn't adopt a narrow, sectarian perspective that denies minorities their basic rights. For the founders and the community at large, establishing an institution requires a significant amount of labour and financial, emotional, and physical strain. To understand minorities' rights to "establish and administer educational institutions," the text cites several Supreme Court decisions that should not be overlooked, and the ability to manage educational institutions.

Founded in 1875 as *Mohammadan Anglo Oriental (MAO)* College by Sir Syed Ahmad Khan, noted Muslim scholar and statesman, it was rechristened as AMU in 1920. Subsequently, JMI was born in the same year, 1920, after having parted ways with AMU. JMI was a result of the strong nationalist commitments of prominent freedom fighters and visionaries like Maulana Mehmud Hasan, Maulana Mohamed Ali, Hakim Ajmal Khan, Mukhtar Ahmad Ansari, and AbdulMajid Khwaja. The fact that JMI survived despite serious fund crunches in its early years following the failure of the Khilafat movement owes much to Gandhi's support for the institution. He had famously told the founding fathers, M A Ansari, Hakim Ajmal Khan, and Abdul Majeed Khwaja that, "The Jamia must run. If you are worried about its finances, I will go about with a begging bowl."

3. AIM & OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The aims along objectives are:

1. To look at the current minority educational Institutions system of management in India.
2. To study the minority educational institutions and judgment in India
3. To study the emerging issues and future needs of minority rights, establishment, and administration to run educational institutions in India.
4. To find out the current challenges and opportunities of minority educational Institutions and the employability-related legal issues, by employers.
5. To find out the employees' litigation related to their pension and other welfare benefits related to the salary PF by the minority institutions.
6. To look at the future support based on the Supreme Court's judgment and order, which may be issued in favour of the minority grounds and enforceable by the state authorities.
7. To study the approvals, recognition, autonomy, aids, stand stand-alone status by the stipulated authorities based on the education courses.
8. To know the future demand at the international level for management education professionals and their importance.
9. To study the Jurisdictional disputes and face challenges at various levels to run the minority institutions.
10. To study the opportunities in the various fields and the specialisation of minority education institutions and intake sheets for different programmes.
11. To study the National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI) Act, 2004, Minority means a community notified as such by the Central Government. The Central Government under the National Commission for Minorities (NCM) Act, 1992 and their roles and rights are directed by the Supreme Court of India, State High Courts, Tribunals and other lower courts.
12. To study the variety of minority based Educational Institutions and their intake seats allocated by the central, state, and union authorities for their facilities.
13. To determine how the constitution functions in this area, when an institution would be considered a minority institution, and the extent of Articles 29 and 30, as well as 350A and 350B of the constitution.
14. To emphasise the minority's ability to create and run their preferred educational institution in relation to both aided and unaided minority educational institutions for the purpose of providing general and professional education to both the minority and non-minority.

15. To investigate how much the State can regulate to maintain control over the minority Institutions.
16. To examine the judicial response in this area.
17. To examine the report of the Sabar Committee for the Educational Upliftment of the Minority.
18. To shed light on the achievements and shortcomings of the Central and State Governments concerning the implementation of various programs and policies for the educational development of the minorities, as well as to acknowledge and critique the function of the National Minorities Commission for the development of the minorities.
19. To avoid maximising their power for minorities' administration, appointments, and other management activities beyond admission, the National Commission for Minorities should consider its future and how to implement parliamentary rules for minorities' institutions and ideas without causing conflict for future generations.

4. MINORITY INSTITUTIONS IN INDIA:

4.1. National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI): As per Section 2 (f) of the National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI) Act, 2004, Minority means a community notified as such by the Central Government. The Central Government under the National Commission for Minorities (NCM) Act, 1992, has notified six religious minority communities, namely Christian, Sikh, Buddhist, Muslim, Parsi, and Jain. The NCMEI grants a Minority Status Certificate to the eligible minority educational institutions that are established and administered by the notified religious minorities (2021)[7].

As on 31.10.2021, the NCMEI has granted Minority Status Certificate to 13,602 Minority Educational Institutions, out of which a total of 5,153 educational institutions is run by the management belonging to the Muslim community, 300 by the Sikh, 7550 by the Christian, 63 by Buddhist, 522 by Jains and 14 by Parsi community. Further, as per the All-India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE), 2019 by the Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Education, the enrolment of minority students in higher education in the last five years has increased from 22,96,671 in 2015-16 to 29,88,610 in 2019-20. As per AISHE, 2019-20 (based on actual response), the total number of teachers belonging to minority communities in the higher educational institutions is 2,18,491.

Further, as per the UDISE+ 2019-20 data of Department of School Education and Literacy, Ministry of Education, out of 50,536 minority schools (including linguistic minorities), 27,259 schools are run by the management belonging to Muslims, 600 by Sikh, 1140 by Jain, 15808 by Christian, 126 by Parsi, 720 by Buddhist and 4883 by Linguistic Minorities & others. UDISE+ does not maintain data separately for Shia, Ahmadia, etc. Further, as per UDISE+, the total enrolment of minority students in schools has increased from 4,44,61,346 in 2018-19 to 4,75,43,853 in 2019-20. Data on the religion of teachers is not maintained.

4.2. Recognised Religious Minority Communities in India:

To aid in the socioeconomic advancement of these populations, the Ministry of Minority Affairs runs several initiatives. "Minority communities" in India are those groups that are formally recognised by the government as such, mainly due to their religious beliefs. A minority is defined as a community that has been notified by the national government under

the National Commission for Minorities (NCM) Act of 1992. There are currently six religious groups that are considered minorities: Christians, Muslims, Sikhs, Buddhists, Jains, and Zoroastrians (Parsis). Indian law grants some social welfare services and protections to these groups.

4.3. Autonomy and State Aid:

In *T.M.A. Pai Foundation v. State of Karnataka*, the Supreme Court held that minority communities have an untrammelled right to establish and administer unaided educational institutions. However, institutions receiving State aid could be subject to government rules and regulations (2002) [9]. The court also ruled that the basic ratio in the *St. Stephen's College v. University of Delhi (AIR 1992 SC 1630)*[17] case, which allowed up to 50% reservation for students belonging to the Christian community, is correct, but a rigid percentage cannot be stipulated (1992) [10].

In *Islamic Academy of Education v. State of Karnataka (2003) 6 SCC 697*[40], the court clarified that each institution is entitled to have its own fee structure, but there can be no profiteering, and capitation fees cannot be charged. The court also emphasized that laws and regulations should not favour majority institutions over minority institutions.

In *P.A. Inamdar v. State of Maharashtra*, the court held that minority educational institutions have a guarantee or assurance to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice. The court emphasized that the right to administer does not include the right to maladministration and that regulatory measures are necessary to maintain educational standards.

4.4. Right to Affiliation:

In *St. Xaviers College v. State of Gujarat* [39], the Supreme Court held that there is no fundamental right to affiliation. However, denying affiliation or recognition except upon certain terms and conditions amounts to the surrender of the right to administer under Article 30(1). The court emphasised that regulatory measures for affiliation are permissible as long as they are reasonable and aimed at maintaining educational standards.

In *N. Ammad v. Emjay High School (1998) 6 SCC 674*[37], the court held that a school which is otherwise a minority school would continue to be so whether the government declared it as such or not. The declaration is only an open acceptance of a legal character that should have existed antecedent to such declaration.

In *Frank Anthony Public School Employees Association v. Union of India (AIR 1987 SC 311)* [38], the Supreme Court observed that the idea of giving special rights to minorities is not to create a privileged section but to provide them with a sense of security and confidence. The court upheld the regulatory measures aimed at making minority institutions effective instruments for imparting education without nullifying the management's rights.

4.5. Minority Status Cases and Orders:

Child Modern Madarsa vs Directorate of Education, Govt. of NCT of Delhi (2024)[11], Govt. of India, National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI) Case No. 407 of 2020. After compliance of the above order, a minority status certificate will be issued accordingly. Given the above, the present petition is disposed of in accordance with this order. Signed, pronounced, and published on Wednesday, 31st Day of January 2024.

At-Qulam English School, V/s Joint Secretary, Minorities Development Department, Mumbai (2024) [12] Direction to the director, Govt. of Bharat, National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI) Case No. 89 of 2021. After compliance of the above order, a minority status certificate be issued accordingly. Given the above, the present petition is disposed of in accordance with this order¹³. Signed, pronounced, and published on Wednesday, 24th Day of January 2024.

4.6. Judgments on Cases:

Based on the case that has been filed against the NCMEI many cases have been filed. ***In 2019***, 2 judgments were given in favour of the minority communities. The case Judgment numbers are as follows. Judgment case 460 of 2019, Judgement case no 487 of 2019, Judgment case 486 of 2019.

In 2020, 21 Judgements against the NCMEI are given below. Judgement case no 69 of 2020, Judgement case no 62 of 2020, Judgement case no 399 of 2020, Judgement case no 307 of 2020, Judgement case no 318 of 2020, Judgement case no 446 of 2020, Judgement case no 436 of 2020, Judgement case no 208 of 2020, Judgement case no 393 of 2020, Judgement case 414 of 2020, Judgement case 435 of 2020, Judgement case 415 of 2020, Judgement case 311 of 2020, Judgement case 291 of 2020, Judgement case 289 of 2020, Judgement case 285 of 2020, Judgement case 190 of 2020, Judgement case 169 of 2020, Judgement case 116 of 2020, Judgement Case no 407 of 2020.

In 2021, 15 Judgements against the NCMEI are given below. Judgment case no 233 of 2021, Judgment case no 02 of 2021, Judgment case no 197 of 2021, Judgement case no 142 of 2021, Judgement case no 13 of 2021, Judgement case no 141 of 2021, Judgement case no 17 of 2021, Judgement case no 18 of 2021, Judgement case no 19 of 2021, Judgement case no 64 of 2021, Judgement case no 113 of 2021, Judgement case 134 of 2021, Judgement case 131 of 2021, Judgement case 102 of 2021, Judgement case 16 of 2021. All judgments are in favour of the minority only.

In 2022, 34 Judgements against the NCMEI are given below. Judgment case no 130 of 2022, Judgement case no 140 of 2022, Judgement case no 71 of 2022, Judgement case 186 of 2022, Judgement case no 163 of 2022, Judgement case no 131 of 2022, Judgement case no 54 of 2022, Judgement case no 252 of 2022, Judgement case no 233 of 2022, Judgement case no 267 of 2022, Judgement case no 234 of 2022, Judgement case no 232 of 2022, Judgement case no 190 of 2022, Judgement case no 58 of 2022, Judgement case no 189 of 2022, Judgement case no 155 of 2022, Judgement case no 60 of 2022, Judgement case no 57 of 2022, Judgement case no 197 of 2022, Judgement case no 172 of 2022, Judgement case no 206 of 2022, Judgement case no 244 of 2022, Judgement case no 265 of 2022, Judgement case no 201 of 2022, Judgement case 204 of 2022, Judgement case 167 of 2022, Judgement case 210 of 2022, Judgement case 182 of 2022, Judgement case 174 of 2022, Judgement case 142 of 2022, Judgement case 141 of 2022, Judgement case 75 of 2022, Judgement case 74 of 2022, Judgement case 35 of 2022. All judgments are in favour of the minority only.

In 2023, 52 Judgements against the NCMEI are given below. Judgement case no 327 of 2023, Judgement case no 212 of 2023, Judgement case no 256 of 2023, Judgement case no 269 of 2023, Judgement case no 103 of 2023, Judgement case no 213 of 2023, Judgement case no 34 of 2023, Judgement case no 09 of 2023, Judgement case no 286 of 2023, Judgement case no 290 of 2023, Judgement case no 346 of 2023, Judgement case no 285 of 2023, Judgement case no 284 of 2023, Judgement case no 268 of 2023, Judgement case no 200 of 2023, Judgement case no 189 of 2023, Judgement case no 126 of 2023, Judgement case no 26 of 2023, Judgement case no 363 of 2023, Judgement case no 362 of 2023,

Judgement case no 357 of 2023, Judgement case no 270 of 2023, Judgement case no 174 of 2023, Judgement case no 173 of 2023, Judgement case no 172 of 2023, Judgement case no 147 of 2023, Judgement case no 142 of 2023, Judgement case no 249 of 2023, Judgement case no 184 of 2023, Judgement case no 183 of 2023, Judgement case no 155 of 2023, Judgement case no 52 of 2023, Judgement case no 03 of 2023, Judgement case 357 of 2023, Judgement case no 100 of 2023, Judgement case no 204 of 2023, Judgement case 119 of 2023, Judgement case no 102 of 2023, Judgement case no 88 of 2023, Judgement case no 139 of 2023, Judgement case no 70 of 2023, Judgement case no 127 of 2023, Judgement case no 128 of 2023, Judgement case no 130 of 2023, Judgement case no 28 of 2023, Judgement case no 98 of 2023, Judgement case no 51 of 2023, Judgement case 81 of 2023, Judgement case 61 of 2023, Judgement case 60 of 2023, Judgement case 59 of 2023, Judgement case 14 of 2023. All judgments are in favour of the minority only.

In 2024, 7 Judgements against the NCMEI are given below. Judgment case no 16 of 2024, Judgment case no 33 of 2024, Judgment case no 14 of 2024, Judgment case no 256 of 2024, Judgment case no 257 of 2024, Judgment case no 213 of 2024, Judgment case no 101 of 2024. All judgments are in favour of the minority only.

4.7. Daily Orders: From January 2025 to May 2025 [13], 51 orders were declared by the Courts. The orders are in favour of the minority communities.

In January 2025, 9 orders were given against the NCMEI [13]. Based on the dates of 14th January 2025, 15th January 2025, 16th January 2025, 21st January 2025, 22 January 2025, 23 January 2025, 28 January 2025, 30th January 2025, 29th January 2025. All orders are in favour of the minority communities.

In February 2025, 8 orders were given against the NCMEI. Based on the dates of 06th February 2025, 04th February 2025, 19th February 2025, 13th February 2025, 12th February 2025, 11th February 2025, 27th February 2025, 25th February 2025. All orders are in favour of the minority communities.

In March 2025, 12 Orders were given against the NCMEI. Based on the dates of 25th March 2025, 04th March 2025, 05th March 2025, 11th March 2025, 18th March 2025, 19th March 2025, 20th March 2025, 06th March 2025, 25th March 2025, 26th March 2025, 27th March 2025, 12th March 2025.

In April 2025, 11 Orders were given against the NCMEI. Based on the dates of 04th March 2025, 05th March 2025, 11th March 2025, 18th March 2025, 19th March 2025, 20th March 2025, 06th March 2025, 25th March 2025, 26th March 2025, 27th March 2025, 12th March 2025.

In May 2025, 11 Orders were given against the NCMEI. Based on the dates of 05th May 2025, 06th May 2025, 07th May 2025, 08th May 2025, 13th May 2025, 14 May 2025, 15 May 2025, 19 May 2025, 20 May 2025, 21 May 2025, 1 May 2025,

4.8. Landmark Judgments:

The legal concept and protection of minority rights, especially in education, have been affected by several significant rulings in India. Cases such as *T.M.A. Pai Foundation vs. State of Karnataka* are examples of this, as they demonstrated that state-level decisions should be made regarding minority status. There was also a lot of court interpretation in the Aligarh Muslim University (AMU) case over what constitutes a minority institution.

State of Karnataka v. T.M.A. Pai Foundation (2002) [14]: This decision made it clear that the state, not the entire country, is the unit used to determine minority status. Accordingly, a group may be considered a minority in one state but not in another. The

decision also focused on minority educational institutions' rights under Article 30 of the Constitution, highlighting their freedom to create and run the institutions of their choosing.

State-wise assessment of minority status was reaffirmed in *Bal Patil v. Union of India (2005)* [41], underscoring the significance of considering linguistic and religious minorities at the state level.

Aligarh Muslim University (AMU) Case (2024) [42]: AMU's minority status was contested in this instance. A seven-judge Supreme Court panel established criteria for figuring out whether a school meets Article 30's requirements for becoming a minority institution. *Azeez Basha v. Union of India (1967)* [43], in which the court had previously declared that AMU was not a minority institution, was also reviewed and overturned.

4.9. Some Popular Landmark Judgments:

1. Orders dated 6.7.2010 relating to Buckley Primary School
2. Orders dated 22.2.2011 relating to Jamia Milia Islamia
3. Orders dated 2.7.2012 relating to Bhalchandra Institute of Education and Management
4. Order dated 27.9.2012 relating to Brown Hills College of Engineering and Technology
5. Order dated 16.1.2013 relating to Association of Minority Pharmacy colleges, Maharashtra
6. Order of the Commission reg. constitutional protection of Article 30(1) to Nayab Abbasi Girls (P.G.) College, Kailsa Road, Amroha, Distt. J.P. Nagar, Uttar Pradesh.
7. Order dated 28.5.2013 relating to Mohd.Ali Jauhar University
8. Milli Talimi Mission Bihar and Ors Vs State of Bihar and Ors. 1984 (4) SCC 500 [68].
9. State of Bihar vs Syed Raza AIR 197 SC 2425 [67].
10. T M A Pai Foundation Vs the State of Karnataka 2002 8 SCC 481 AIR 2003 SC 355.

4.10. Students' Admissions:

St. Stephen's college v. University of Delhi [17] came up before the Supreme Court in the year 1992 for judgement wherein it was held that *minority aided educational institutions may preserve 50 per cent seats for their community candidates and are entitled to give them preference in admission as it is necessary to maintain the minority character of institutions.*

In *Satimbla Sharma v. St. Paul's Senior Secondary School* [18], the Supreme Court held that an unaided private minority school over which the government has no administrative control because of their autonomy under Article 30(1) of the Constitution are not "State" within the meaning of Article 12 of the Constitution. Hence, they are not subject to the public law obligation of the State under Article 14 and Article 39(d).

4.11. Common Admission Tests:

The Supreme Court in *Modern Dental College and Research Centre v. State of Madhya Pradesh* [19] again held that private unaided minority institutions have the right to devise a rational manner of selecting and admitting students. However, a certain degree of state control is required since the State must ensure that high standards of education are maintained in all professional institutions.

In the famous case of *T.M.A. Pai Foundation v. State of Karnataka*[20] the Supreme Court held that an aided minority educational institution would be entitled to have the right of admission of students belonging to the minority group. The reservation policy of the government cannot be imposed on aided or unaided minority educational institutions, and to unaided non-minority educational institutions.

A *Seven Judge Bench of the Supreme Court in the case of P.A. Inamdar v. State of Maharashtra* [21] discussed the entire gamut of Law about minority educational institutions and noticed that the right conferred by Article 30 was more like protection for minorities. It protects minority institutions from regulatory legislations framed under Article 19 (6), but still, they were not immune to regulatory control. The Supreme Court was basically concerned with admission of the students to different institutions, wherein it observed that even within the scope of Article 30(1), there was a need for imposing reasonable restrictions even on the minority institution, and such direction would not vitiate and hurt the minority status.

The *Supreme Court of India in the case of Christian Medical College Vellore Association v. Union of India* [22] observed that Article 30 aligns with other parts of the Constitution and the regulatory measures of the government agencies do not impinge on the rights of the educational institutions, including the institutions managed by the minority communities. The conduct of Common Admission Tests for admission to various academic programmes does not violate the rights of educational institutions, including the minority educational institutions. The Supreme Court observed thus:

“The rights of religious minorities under Article 30 of the Constitution have also been clarified to be not in conflict with other parts of the Constitution, as balancing the rights is constitutional intendment in the national interest. The regulatory measures under the Act and the Regulation cannot be said to be averse to the interest of such institutions, and such reasonable measures can be carved out. Additionally, these regulatory measures do not impinge upon the rights of institutions guaranteed under Articles 14, 19(1)(g), 25 and 30 of the Constitution. The Constitution provides a limitation on the power of the State to interfere with life, liberty and rights; however, the concept of limited government cannot be extended to a level where it defeats national interest. The regulatory framework created by the Act/ Dentist Act is concomitant with conditions, affiliation and recognition, and providing central examination in the form of NEET cannot be said to be violative of the rights under Articles 19(1)(g) and 30 of the Constitution.

The uniform entrance examination cannot be said to be an unreasonable regulatory framework. Considering the terms and conditions for affiliation and recognition for professional medical and such other professional courses are binding, and no relaxation can be permitted in the conditions. The rights under Articles 19(1)(g) and 30 read with Articles 25, 26 and 29(1) of the Constitution do not come in the way of securing transparency and recognition of merits in the matter of admissions. It is open to the State to regulate the course of study, qualifications for ensuring educational standards and imposing reasonable restrictions in the national and public interest (2016) [32]”.

4.12. Admission Fee and Other Fees:

In *Unni Krishnan v. State of A.P.*[23], it was held by the Supreme Court that the minority educational institutions may charge such a fee as is required for the betterment and growth of the institution, but they should not be an element of profiteering in fixing the fee. But the question arises, who should audit the reasonability of the fee and the element of profiteering? Many of the minority institutions took advantage of this judgment, and the minority students were subjected to exploitation. The meritorious students could not pursue their education because they could not pay the exorbitant, arbitrary and unregulated fee charged by the minority institutions. This was a case of exploitation of minorities at the hands of minorities.

But in the case of *Islamic Academy of Education v. State of Karnataka* [24], the Supreme Court directed to constitution of a separate committee in each state to be headed by a retired judge of the high court, to examine and recommend the fee structure of the minority educational institutions.

Again, the issue of the fee charged by the minority educational institutions came up before the *Supreme Court in Cochin University of Science and Technology vs Thomas Joan* [25], wherein it was held that a minority educational institution must be left to its own devices in the matter of fixation of fees. Profiteering or capitation fee is not permissible, but some amount of surplus fund is permissible. If the institution follows broad principles, it is not required to explain minutely the details of its receipts and expenses. Again, the judiciary tilted towards the management of minority educational institutions, but this is not in favour of the larger interest of the minority students or the community in general. Such judgements are prone to be misused by the management of Minority education institutions. Now the question arises, who shall audit and determine the *permissible limit of surplus fund (2021)*[31].

4.13. Medium of Instruction:

Minorities have the right to teach their children in their native tongue, according to the Supreme Court's ruling in *State of Bombay v. Bombay Educational Society* [26].

In *D. A. V. College v. State of Punjab* [27], the Supreme Court noted that the power granted by Article 30(1) to create and run any kind of educational institution encompasses the ability to select the medium of instruction. However, the minority educational institution must still choose the teachers themselves, even though the university can specify requirements for the academic staff.

A larger *Supreme Court bench was tasked with hearing the State of Karnataka v. Associated Management of English Medium Primary & Secondary Schools* [28] case in July 2013. On May 6, 2014, the Supreme Court ruled that a five-judge panel could not compel linguistic minorities to use their mother tongue exclusively as the medium of instruction. What the Court noted was as follows:

According to Article 30(1) of the Constitution, we have previously ruled that a linguistic minority has the right to select the medium of instruction used for instruction in the primary grades of the school that it has founded. In breach of this basic right under Article 30(1), Article 350A cannot be read to provide the State the authority to require a linguistic minority to select its mother language as the only medium of instruction in a primary school that it has created. Accordingly, we maintain that the State cannot force linguistic minorities to select their mother tongue as the only medium of instruction in elementary schools under Article 350A of the Constitution. Given our responses to the questions posed before us, we are dismissing Civil Appeal Nos. 5166-5190 of 2013, 5191-5199 of 2013, the Writ Petition (C) No.290 of 2009, and the Civil Appeal resulting from S.L.P. (C) No.32858 of 2013.

4.14. The RTE Act of 2009 Does Not Apply to Minority Institutions:

The *Supreme Court ruled in Society for Unaided Private Schools of Rajasthan vs Union of India* [29] that unaided minority schools are exempt from the 2009 Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act. Article 30(1) guarantees unassisted minority schools a fundamental right that is violated by the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, specifically Sections 12(1)(c) and 18(3).

In *Pramati Educational and Cultural Trust v. Union of India* [30], a five-judge Supreme Court bench looked at whether the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, did not apply to institutions run and owned by minority communities. They concluded that: Therefore, we maintain that clause (5) of Article 15 of the Constitution

has not affected any of the rights outlined in Articles 14, 19,(1)(g), and 21. Additionally, Bhandari, J.'s opinion in *Ashoka Kumar Thakur v. Union of India* (above) that the Ninety-third Amendment's imposition of reservation on unaided institutions has nullified Article 19(1)(g), a fundamental aspect of the Constitution, is incorrect. Rather, we maintain that the Constitution's (93rd Amendment) Act, 2005, which included clause (5) to Article 15, is lawful. (Para 29).

Ultra virus the Constitutions: The Constitution (Ninety-third Amendment) Act of 2005, which added clause (5) to Article 15 of the Constitution, and the Constitution (Eighty-Sixth Amendment) Act of 2002, which added Article 21A to the Constitution, do not change the fundamental framework or structure of the Constitution and are therefore deemed to be constitutionally valid. Additionally, we maintain that the 2009 Act does not violate Article 19(1)(g) of the Constitution. But we believe that the 2009 Act goes beyond the Constitution because it pertains to minority schools, whether they are assisted or not, as defined by Article 30 clause (1). Consequently, the Muslim Minority Schools Managers' Association's Writ Petition (C) No. 1081 of 2013 is granted, while the non-minority private unaided educational institutions' Writ Petition (C) Nos. 416 of 2012, 152 of 2013, 60 of 2014, 95 of 2014, 106 of 2014, 128 of 2014, 144 of 2014, 145 of 2014, 160 of 2014, and 136 of 2014 are denied.

4.15. Age of Superannuation in Minority Educational Institutions:

The Bombay High Court rendered a decision in the case of *Shri K.P. Shukla & Others v. The State of Maharashtra & Others* [35] on January 10, 1997. The State Government's decision to award their institution minority status was contested by the petitioners, assistant teachers at Mumbai's Shri Sanatan Dharm High School and Junior College. The main points of contention were the Maharashtra Employees of Private Schools (Conditions of Service) Rules, 1981's applicability, specifically the headmaster's superannuation age and the management's right to keep the headmaster on staff past the retirement age. Rules' obligatory retirement age, beyond which an employee is required to leave their job. This age is set at 58 in this instance by Rule 17 for workers who are not Class IV employees.

The ruling in *Shri K.P. Shukla & Others v. The State of Maharashtra & Others by the Bombay High Court* [35] upholds the rule that state laws intended to uphold educational standards are acceptable and do not violate the constitutional rights of institutions serving underrepresented groups. By maintaining Rule 17, the court struck a balance between the state's desire to guarantee educational effectiveness and quality and the autonomy of minority institutions. For upcoming situations where state restrictions and minority institutions' rights collide, this ruling is a crucial point of reference.

The High Court investigated the applicability of the State Government's superannuation age requirements for minority educational institutions under Rule 17 of the Maharashtra Employees of Private Schools (Conditions of Service) Rules, 1981. The petitioners argued that because their school is a minority institution, it should be excluded from these regulations, particularly regarding the headmaster's mandatory retirement age. The legitimacy of extending state restrictions to minority institutions was assessed by the court by examining the applicable constitutional provisions, the statutory framework, and previous case law. The High Court examined whether Rule 17 of the *Maharashtra Employees of Private Schools (Conditions of Service) Rules, 1981* [44], which outlines the State Government's superannuation age restrictions for minority educational institutions, was applicable. As a minority institution, the petitioners contended that their school ought to be exempt from these rules, especially the one pertaining to the headmaster's required retirement age [66]. The court evaluated whether it was legitimate to impose state limits on minority institutions by looking at the relevant constitutional clauses, the legislative framework, and prior case law (1997) [33].

4.16. No Capitation Fee for Professional Courses:

Modern Dental College and Research Centre & others vs State of Madhya Pradesh and others [34], Supreme Court Judgment in 2016. It is prohibited to charge a capitation fee and to utilise any seat in exchange for payment of the capitation cost. One must distinguish between a "business" or a simple "occupation" and a "vocation." A profession is largely a service to society, with earnings being incidental or secondary, but there is a profit motivation in commerce and, to a certain extent, in occupation. Once a student has earned a professional degree through the payment of a capitation fee, they are likely to prioritize earning over serving, which is detrimental to society. Unaided minority and non-minority institutions are simply not allowed to charge a capitation fee for professional courses. Profiteering is likewise prohibited. Notwithstanding the legal stance, this Court cannot ignore the harsh facts of the commercialization of education and the unethical methods used by several institutions to generate substantial profits for their own personal or self-serving objectives. Regulation of the admissions process is necessary to ensure that students are not taken advantage of and that admissions are made based on merit and transparency, if capitation fees and profiteering are to be prevented. To accomplish the aforementioned goal, entry and cost structures may be regulated (2016) [34].

4.17. Staff Selection Procedure for Minority Institutions:

The management of these professional, unaided institutions will have the authority to choose instructors based on the requirements and eligibility requirements set forth by the state or university, provided that a logical selection process is followed. In order to avoid being able to levy a capitation fee, management should adopt a reasonable price structure. A fair surplus for the advancement of education is acceptable, but the State or institution can design the right machinery to guarantee that there is no profiteering and that no capitation fee is applied. Requirements for accreditation or affiliation may generally address academic and educational issues, such as the well-being of instructors and students. *Modern Dental College and Research Centre & others vs State of Madhya Pradesh and others* (2016) [34].

4.18. All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) Rule for Minority Institutions:

Ensuring minority institutions can build and operate educational institutions while adhering to general educational standards and minority rights principles is the primary objective of the AICTE's [36] (All India Council for Technical Education) guidelines. These requirements cover registration, organizational structure, admissions processes, and compliance with relevant laws and regulations. The AICTE provides recommendations. These guidelines must be followed by all AICTE-accredited institutions, regardless of whether they are minority or non-minority colleges. All AICTE-accredited colleges are required to follow the rules that the AICTE provides for its colleges, which are updated regularly (2025) [36].

5. METHODOLOGY:

The researcher gathered information about minority institutes from a variety of sources, including relevant court orders, government agencies, forums, and commission directives. Minority institutions' rights, establishment, management, appointment, superannuation, pensions, and other welfare are all intertwined with major instances. The Common Entrance Test, government seat distribution, and admission of intakes by minority rights are all based on the minority grounds of articles 29 and 30 of the Indian Constitution. The Majority of the judgments and orders are granted in favour of minority grounds to run and maintain the uninterrupted operation of the institutions. All case laws are referenced and

taken into the researcher considerations and have been included in the respective place of this article for future use and jurisdictional action for additional processes at their end.

The researcher has adopted the doctrinal method and tried to analyse legal propositions, legal framework, and case laws, and presented them systematically and logically. The researcher has made an analytical study on the focus of cultural and educational rights of the minorities, keeping in mind the concept of minority and the rights belonging to them in the sphere of establishment and administration of minority institutions of their choice. There is the formal view of the researcher that to register their fundamental rights and jurisdictional authority must be take a necessary and mandatory support must be provided for the minority institutions.

6. DATA ANALYSIS:

6.1. Minority Rights: To comply with the regulations and manage minority educational institutions under Articles 29 and 30, the Supreme Court of India issued several rulings and directives to the state and the federal government. There have been numerous orders issued between 1915 and 2025. However, the Supreme Court rendered most of the rulings and decisions between 2023 and 2007, and they were based on Articles 29 and 30 of the Indian Constitution.

Fig.1. Supreme Court of India Sources: IK^[15]

Minority rights disputes have arisen in many cases before the Madras High Court. Many of the cases that occurred in 2022 and 2023 were 60 and above.

Fig.2. Madras High Court. Sources: IK^[15]

Fig.3. Delhi High Court. Sources: IK^[15]

The Delhi High Court cases, which were 20 and up, are compared to the Madras High Court at a lower level.

Fig.4. Allahabad High Court Sources: IK^[15]

The state and central government agencies have received several directives and rulings from the Allahabad High Court to follow the guidelines outlined in the Indian Constitution. Major disputes have been settled in 2019–2021.

Fig.5. Bombay High Court Sources: IK^[15]

Many institutions were ordered by the Bombay High Court to abide by government regulations, which is against articles 29 and 30 of the Constitution. In violation of the constitution and educational institutions, the court has arbitrarily issued such orders to minority institutions.

Fig.6. Overall Declarations by the Indian High Courts from various states. Sources: IK^[15]

6.2. State-Wise Minority Certified Educational Institutes in India: The Government of India, Ministry of Education, Department of Higher Education, National Commission for

Minority Educational Institutions, New Delhi has published the statistical data based on state, year, and minority certificates issued to the Institutes around the Indian States on 31 March 2025. The majority of the institutions were established by the state of Kerala in 2011, is 852, and in 2012, there were 843. Uttar Pradesh is the second place to establish many institutions in 2012, is 692, and in 2013, there were 513 institutions that received minority certificates for their welfare.

STATE-WISE AND YEAR-WISE DETAILS OF MINORITY STATUS CERTIFICATES ISSUED																										
Sl. No.	STATE	YEAR WISE BREAK UP																							2025	Total No. of
		2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024					
1	Andaman	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Andhra Pradesh	0	2	5	2	21	0	5	17	31	55	56	24	16	2	0	0	0	2	4	9	1	252	1	252	
3	Arunachal Pradesh	0	0	2	0	6	0	0	12	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24
4	Assam	0	2	0	17	2	13	111	32	16	9	7	5	3	4	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	224	0	224	
5	Bihar	1	2	20	17	3	3	27	6	15	10	12	14	14	4	0	0	3	5	3	6	0	165	0	165	
6	Chandigarh	0	2	3	1	1	1	3	1	4	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	
7	Chhattisgarh	0	1	4	5	7	55	91	3	24	28	10	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	235	0	235
8	D&N Haveli	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
9	Daman	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
10	Dalhi	2	36	8	15	10	14	33	37	28	27	12	23	4	0	2	0	2	2	1	5	2	263	0	263	
11	Goa	0	9	31	28	81	4	3	3	0	2	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	165	
12	Gujarat	0	3	3	5	8	5	5	0	2	4	7	13	3	4	0	0	0	0	4	2	0	68	0	68	
13	Haryana	0	20	12	3	4	0	24	23	27	13	16	18	9	11	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	182	0	182	
14	Himachal Pradesh	0	9	3	4	0	1	3	3	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	28	
15	Jharkhand	0	2	15	13	3	1	4	15	21	11	6	10	3	2	0	0	0	0	9	7	1	123	0	123	
16	Karnataka	0	4	25	15	11	9	12	43	105	186	157	84	43	20	0	1	12	15	17	1	751	0	751		
17	Kerala	0	9	78	37	524	822	852	843	493	454	262	147	73	32	1	0	3	16	11	5	0	4722	0	4722	
18	Lakshadweep	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
19	Madhya Pradesh	0	15	19	12	23	23	58	73	64	62	49	43	45	29	5	15	24	22	9	0	0	595	0	595	
20	Maharashtra	11	22	28	21	7	3	2	17	37	21	4	15	10	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	202	0	202	
21	Manipur	0	1	0	1	0	0	32	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	37	0	37
22	Meghalaya	0	1	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	8
23	Mizoram	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
24	Nagaland	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
25	Orissa	0	14	16	23	6	12	6	2	4	4	1	21	11	1	0	0	1	0	8	1	0	131	0	131	
26	Pondicherry	0	2	13	0	3	0	0	1	1	0	1	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	29	0	29	
27	Punjab	0	11	39	4	0	3	5	7	13	14	14	3	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	126	0	126	
28	Rajasthan	0	2	22	37	20	4	2	0	4	8	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	105	0	105
29	Sikkim	0	3	13	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	18
30	Tamil Nadu	1	9	19	13	14	15	12	23	56	86	200	240	160	107	0	13	41	30	67	0	1121	0	1121		
31	Telangana	4	7	19	4	3	2	12	18	40	66	79	71	5	0	0	0	0	3	4	4	0	352	0	352	
32	Tripura	0	0	0	1	6	0	0	4	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	13
33	Uttar Pradesh	1	107	99	48	59	114	253	692	593	435	183	366	164	59	3	4	6	13	31	47	10	3287	0	3287	
34	Uttarakhand	0	36	17	8	4	3	11	4	6	8	10	6	5	4	0	0	0	3	3	2	1	131	0	131	
35	West Bengal	1	85	215	113	15	7	89	86	74	7	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	697	0	697	
Total		21	422	737	507	848	1122	1656	1565	1672	1516	1095	1122	580	289	12	11	44	123	150	190	17	14099	0	14099	

Tab 1. State-wise, Community-wise & year-wise details of minority status certified Educational Institutions. Sources: NCMEI^[13]

6.3. Community-wise Minority status certificates issued to the Institutes in India:

Six minorities have been identified as major minority populations in India based on statistics given by the NCMEI. Christian minority institutions have been granted 7631 certificates, followed by Muslim minority with 5236, Jain institutions with 576, Sikh institutions with 312, Buddhist institutions with 67, and Parsi institutions with just 15. The majority of minority institutions are therefore Christian and Muslim.

COMMUNITY-WISE AND YEAR-WISE DETAILS OF MINORITY STATUS CERTIFICATES ISSUED																										
Sl. No.	COMMUNITY	YEAR WISE BREAK UP																							2025	Total No. of
		2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024					
1	Buddhist	0	0	1	5	0	1	17	29	6	0	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	67	0	67		
2	Christian	3	384	636	388	726	910	1101	784	536	505	655	469	301	133	2	3	11	53	94	129	8	7831	0	7831	
3	Jain	0	0	1	4	4	13	33	69	60	56	34	129	63	35	5	6	12	21	18	7	2	576	0	576	
4	Muslim	17	34	96	106	106	185	471	1044	1018	914	384	469	196	103	4	1	18	43	35	49	5	5236	0	5236	
5	Parsi	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	3	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	15	0	15		
6	Sikh	1	4	3	4	12	12	32	39	52	41	18	50	15	13	1	1	2	5	2	3	2	312	0	312	
Total		21	422	737	507	848	1122	1656	1565	1672	1516	1095	1122	580	289	12	11	44	123	150	190	17	14099	0	14099	

Tab 2. Community-wise & year-wise details of minority status certified Educational Institutions. Sources: NCMEI^[13]

6.4. Appointing Staff in Minority Institutions:

8250 cases are argued in around Indian judiciary from 1968 to 2025. In 2004 and 2009, the Supreme Court declared judgments against the NCMEI. Based on the minority rights, the honouree supremacy judges declare the right of the national under articles 29 and 30. The religious have full rights to administer, establish, and run the educational institutions in their states. It also helps the national growth and reduces illiteracy. The educational institutions show their growth and pupil enlightenment and take on their challenges to develop national growth in every sector.

Fig.7. Supreme Court Judgments and orders in favour of Minority Educational Institutions. Sources: IK^[15]

6.5. Pension seeking in the Minority Institutions: The original petitioners from Orissa W.P.(C) No.17067 of 2023In the matter of an application under Articles 226 and 227 of the Constitution of India filed by **Hemant Kumar Chhotarary vs State of Odissa** [45]. Therefore, this Court is of the view that the rejection of the Petitioners' claim to get the benefit in the light of the order passed in the case of Sarat Chandra Parida is not sustainable in the eye of law and accordingly all those orders rejecting the claim of the Petitioners to get the benefit of pension and other pensionary benefits under 1981 Rules is hereby quashed. While quashing all those orders in the //181// respective writ petitions, this Court held that the Petitioners are entitled to get the benefit of pension and other pensionary benefits as has been extended in favour of Sarat Chandra Parida. This Court accordingly directs Opp. Parties to extend the benefit of pension and other pensionary benefits as due and admissible in terms of the provisions contained under Rule 3 of the 1981 Rules in favour of the Petitioners within three (3) months from the date of receipt of this order declared by Biraja Prasanna Satapathy, Judge Orissa High Court, Cuttack Dated the 12th of January, 2024/Sangita & Sneha Location: High Court of Orissa, Cuttack.

Fig.8. Field cases in Odisha Courts for pension claimed in Minority Educational Institutions. Sources: IK^[15]

Regarding the claim of pension from the aided and non-aided minority institutions in 2024, 1499 cases have been filed in various courts from different states in India. 504 cases are from the state of Orissa. 229 cases from Karnataka, 111 cases from Madras, 83 cases from Bombay, 64 Cases from Delhi, 147 cases from Rajasthan, 39 Cases from Madhya Pradesh, 42 Cases from Jharkhand, 71 Cases from Patna. Out of the 1499 cases, 19 cases are argued in the Supreme Court of India and declared the Judgement based on the grounds. Many Judgments are in favour of the minority Institutions.

6.6. Minority States certified by the NCMEI: 14147 Educational Institutions that have been issued a Minority Status Certificate by the National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions up to 30.06.2025. There were 68 Buddhists, 7862 Christians Minority Institutions. 582 to Jain, 5308 to Muslim, 15 to Parsi, and 313 to Sikh. Totally 14147 Cases have been filed by the minority institutions to run their institutes smoothly without any hindrances (2025) [16].

7. DISCUSSION:

Aided Minority Institutions Have Absolute Right to Appoint Principals, Teachers; DoE Can Only Prescribe Qualification & Experience (2024) [8]: Delhi HC Judge Hari Shankar said that The Delhi High Court has ruled that aided minority institutions have an absolute right to appoint the principals, teachers, and other staff in the educational institutions run by them. “The grant of aid, by the State, to the minority institution, makes no substantial difference to this legal position. At the highest, the State can regulate the proper utilization of the aid which it grants, etc.

The High Court investigated the applicability of the State Government's superannuation age requirements for minority educational institutions under Rule 17 of the Maharashtra Employees of Private Schools (Conditions of Service) Rules, 1981. The petitioners argued that because their school is a minority institution, it should be excluded from these regulations, particularly regarding the headmaster's mandatory retirement age. The legitimacy of extending state restrictions to minority institutions was assessed by the court by examining the applicable constitutional provisions, the statutory framework, and previous case law. The High Court examined whether Rule 17 of the Maharashtra Employees of Private Schools (Conditions of Service) Rules, 1981, which outlines the State Government's superannuation age restrictions for minority educational institutions, was applicable. As a minority institution, the petitioners contended that their school ought to be exempt from these rules, especially the one pertaining to the headmaster's required retirement age. The court evaluated whether it was legitimate to impose state limits on minority institutions by looking at the relevant constitutional clauses, the legislative framework, and prior case law.

8. HYPOTHESIS:

H₁: It encourages the preservation of their cultural and linguistic identity by giving minority institutions the authority to create and run educational institutions.

H₂: In the educational system, diversity and inclusivity are promoted by minority institutions' autonomy.

H₃: Social justice and equality cannot be achieved without defending minority rights, including those pertaining to education.

H₄: The prevention of discrimination and marginalization of minority communities is greatly aided by minority institutions.

H₅: Minority rights advocates contend that special treatment for underprivileged groups whether through affirmative action, legal exemptions, public endorsement of cultural customs, or political autonomy, is necessary for fairness.

H₆: The goal of minority rights is to protect unique identities while making sure that any unfair treatment of groups or members of those groups does not cover up discriminatory behaviors and laws.

H₇: The four pillars of minority rights are equality and non-discrimination, the right to effective participation, protection of existence, and protection and promotion of identity. The ICCPR is a key source for defending the rights of minorities under both Article 27 and Article 30 of the CRC.

H₈: The minorities are allowed to create and run educational institutions; the constitution makes no mention of their right to affiliation.

9. FINDINGS:

1. The majority of minority institutions are therefore Christian, followed by Muslim.
2. The minority rights, the honouree supremacy judges declare the rights of the Indian constitution under articles 29 and 30.
3. Unaided private minority Institutions over which the government has no administrative control because of their autonomy under Article 30(1) of the Constitution are not “State” within the meaning of Article 12 of the Constitution.
4. Many of the institutions were established by the state of Kerala and Uttar Pradesh in 2011 to 2013, which received minority certificates for their welfare.
5. The claim of pension from the aided and non-aided minority institutions in 2024 is barred for non-aided institutions.
6. Most of the cases are filed against the government of Odisha state.
7. The superannuation for minority institutions is granted up to 58 years.
8. Aided and non-aided minority institutions have the absolute right to Appoint Principals and teachers; DoE/University Can Only Prescribe qualifications & Experience.
9. It is prohibited to charge a capitation fee and to utilise any seat in exchange for payment of the capitation cost.
10. Unaided minority institutions are exempt from the 2009 Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act.
11. Minorities have the right to teach their children in their native tongue, according to the Supreme Court's rules.
12. The Supreme Court held that the minority educational institutions may charge such a fee as is required for the betterment and growth of the institution, but they should not be an element of profiteering in fixing the fee.
13. The conduct of Common Admission Tests (CAT) for admission to various academic programmes does not violate the rights of educational institutions, including the minority educational institutions.
14. The Minority aided educational institutions may preserve 50 per cent seats for their community candidates and are entitled to give them preference in admission, as it is necessary to maintain the minority character of institutions.
15. The Supreme Court emphasised that regulatory measures for affiliation are permissible as long as they are reasonable and aimed at maintaining educational standards.
16. The Supreme Court held that minority communities have an untrammelled right to establish and administer unaided educational institutions. However, institutions receiving State aid could be subject to government rules and regulations.
17. Many cases are highlighted that minority institutions have the right to establish, administer, and run educational institutions and the right to receive grants from the government and respective agencies.

10. SUGGESTIONS:

Enforcing Article 30 Minority Rights: According to legal news sources, the courts have repeatedly upheld minority institutions' freedom to create and run the educational institutions of their choosing. This right permits appropriate governmental regulation while also extending to the selection of professors, curriculum, and entrance requirements. Fair

treatment and the prevention of prejudice against minority communities are the goals of Article 30, as the courts have underlined.

Juris Suggestions (2025) [46]: The courts must always defend minorities' rights because, as Justice N. Anand Venkatesh observed, "the dawn of India's independence heralded a profound commitment to safeguarding the rights of minorities, instilling a sense of security amid apprehensions about their future in a newly sovereign nation." According to the judge, Article 30(1) of the Constitution, which mentions religious and linguistic minorities' rights to create and run the educational institutions of their choosing, is more about providing protection to the minority than acknowledging their rights. There was more to this clause than just a formality. The Constitution's founders pledged to safeguard minority communities' cultural and educational identity. at situations where these rights are at danger, constitutional courts must step in forcefully to uphold the fundamental principles of equality and justice and to reaffirm this commitment," he stated. The judge continued by saying: "The judiciary must acknowledge its crucial role in reestablishing trust among minorities by serving as a guardian of the rights that were promised to them, thereby reinforcing the very essence of India's democratic ethos and its dedication to unity in diversity." He noted that the appointment of assistant professors and principals in minority-run educational institutions would not be subject to the University Grants Commission (UGC) Regulations, 2018, and the ensuing Government Order issued by the Tamil Nadu Government on January 11, 2021, for adopting those regulations.

A group of writ petitions against the University of Madras and Annamalai University's refusal to approve the appointment of 66 assistant professors and a principal due to noncompliance with the UGC Regulations, 2018 were filed by Women's Christian College, Madras Christian College, Loyola College, and Stella Maris College in Chennai, as well as the Sacred Heart Arts and Science College in the Villupuram district. Such writ petitions were granted. As long as the appointees have the necessary professional and educational credentials, the Supreme Court has recognized minority educational institutions' right to select their own teaching staff, according to a series of rulings. The judge agreed with senior counsel Isaac Mohanlal, who was representing the petitioner institutions. In the 2011 case of Forum of Minority Institutions and Associations versus State of Tamil Nadu, a Division Bench of the High Court decided that minority educational institutions would not be subject to the UGC Regulations of 2000 and 2010, which require the creation of selection committees with outside members, such as vice-chancellor's nominees. The judge ruled that the 2018 [3] regulations would also not apply to minority institutions because they require the creation of such selection committees prior to the appointment of teaching personnel. He claimed that the minority institutions' ability to run their business would be diminished if outsiders were included on the selection committee.

Article 29 & 30: Our framers of the Constitution (1980) [47] made a deliberate effort to guarantee that the spirit of pluralism was preserved by fundamental rights, as seen by clauses like Article 30(1).²⁹ Therefore, in addition to their special status under the Constitution, they also had a "additional fundamental right"³⁰ that was to be interpreted as far as possible. In general, the rights of minorities are collective rights [48]. However, there isn't a standard definition or foundation for classification [49]. Since it was left to the courts' expertise to define the parameters of minority rights, they were entrusted with filling in this purposeful void [50]. They have attempted to define what it means to be a linguistic or religious minority in a broad sense on a few instances, but even these pronouncements have

their own challenges [51]. However, this essay does not ignore the significant issues caused by the lack of clarity in the definition of the term "minority." In this article, the state's regulation of minority educational institutions is examined from a constitutional perspective.

Appointment: Government processes determine how principals and/or teachers are appointed in minority educational institutions [52]. The category of issues sometimes referred to as "internal administration" includes teacher appointment matters. certain rules and guidelines should only serve the stated objectives in certain circumstances and should not "deprive the founders of the institution to manage and Mold the institution according to their need, desire, and object "[53 & 54]. A statutory authority's regulatory license has been abused as a result of the exercise of absolute powers. This contradicts the fundamental tenets of independent minority schools.

Holly Cullen [69] proposes a theoretical framework to address what she perceives to be an inevitable conflict between minority rights and education rights, although in a different setting. She suggests that minority education rights be seen as a subset of education rights rather than minority rights when determining whether they are better classified as education rights or minority rights. According to her, the goal of educational excellence would yield to the preservation of the cultural features of the minority group in question if minority education rights were seen as a type of minority rights [55]. This strategy, however, makes a false and needless division between the rights of minorities and those of education. Indian courts have unambiguously stated that the state is not entirely prohibited from intervening in the management of minority educational institutions. In light of this, it is not necessary to view minority rights and educational rights as separate. Minorities can manage educational institutions with the dual goals of advancing educational excellence and defending minority values, as opposed to working in fields that are mutually exclusive. According to normative principles, the state can always step in to protect one goal from being overshadowed or compromised in the service of another if any of these are in danger. This strategy would protect equality of opportunity in the management of these organizations and encourage pluralistic principles.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS:

For Government: Although minority institutions are required to adhere to state norms and standards [56], the existence of rights is contingent upon the state's actions [57]. The state must work to guarantee minorities' cultural and educational rights in order to foster mutual trust, since this is the yardstick by which their freedom and dignity are measured [58]. Unfortunately, these goals can still be considered constitutional aspirations as a result of the contested ruling.

For Judges: Examining the above-described range of rulings, the Supreme Court has upheld rights under Article 30(1) [59]. P.M. Bakshi[60] is in favour of regulations that promote "smooth working and educational excellence." When examining the Supreme Court's methodology, he identifies some patterns that, while theoretically sound, turn into controversial issues when put into practice [61].

For Jurisdiction: The Jurisdictional authority passes the suitable direction to amend the special procedure to allocate the seats for reserved categories by the parliament and gets approved by the president to be enacted through the concerned agencies. According to legal experts, courts may also take social justice and inclusion into account when determining whether restrictions impacting minority institutions are legitimate, especially when it comes to reservations for underserved groups.

12. CONCLUSION:

The Supreme Court issued criteria on November 8, 2024, for evaluating whether an educational institution founded by a linguistic or religious minority qualifies as a minority under Article 30. The right of "all minorities to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice" is stated in this article. Minorities have the freedom to establish and manage whatever kind of educational institution they choose, according to Article 30 of the Indian Constitution. Minority educational institutions (MEIs) are granted particular safeguards under this, enabling them to establish their own admissions policies and other regulations. The Court said that even though St Stephen's College in Delhi is funded by the government, it can still claim minority status because it was set up by a religious community. The minority educational institutions were exempted from reserving seats for Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST) under Article 15(5). If the minority institutions do not have the right to represent the SC and ST community, without the rights, how can they be called minority institutions? If they are registered under the SC/ST categories, they have full rights to reserve for the special categories of SC or ST. So, the Jurisdictions must look at the minority institutions once again and revoke the previous judgment or orders and pass a suitable order to regulate through the concerned authorities.

Scheduled groups are receiving reservations from government agencies based on preference. Due to their creation by the state or federal government, they offer all amenities to the employees and pupils. However, they find that insufficient. Minority institutions follow the regulations and have access to all the facilities provided to the public, unlike government institutions.

In the same vein, minority organizations are exercising their right to open educational establishments. The state or federal government independently reserves seats. Minority institutions are not authorized by the jurisdiction to allocate seats to restricted groups. This is targeted aimed against the minority communities. So, if minority rights are not appropriately made in the constitution, the respective court to utilize its power and ask the parliament to enact to process, the relevant jurisdiction's instruction to pass the order to the corresponding government and draft an adjustment that would be suitable for minority institutions as a new amendment. The supreme Jurisdictions imposed to make the change must be authorized by the president to be adopted within the specified period.

Minority educational institutions can significantly contribute to the preservation of cultural legacy, the advancement of educational equity, and the empowerment of future generations by putting these ideas into practice.

The number of educational institutions for underrepresented groups has grown during the past few decades [62]. Generally, under Article 30(1), minority institutions aim for greater autonomy than non-minority institutions [63]. It is possible to restrict minority rights in any case [64]. However, targeting minority communities cannot be done by abusing the fundamental constitutional concept of equal respect for all religions [65].

REFERENCE:

- [1] Kuldip Singh (1994): *S. R. Bommai v. Union of India* on 11 March 1994. AIR 1918, 1994 SCC (3) 1.1976. Supreme Court of India. <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/60799/>
- [2] Praveen Swami (1997): Protecting secularism and federal fair play. Published on 1 Nov 1997. <https://frontline.thehindu.com/other/article30160299.ece>
- [3] Himani Singh (2018): The right of minorities to set up and govern their own educational institution. Bhartiya Vidyapeeth University. Published on May 7th, 2018. <https://blog.ipleaders.in/minority-educational-institution-constitution/#comment-109396>.
- [4] Chishti, Seema (2016) "Simply Put: 'Minority' Status for AMU, Jamia Millia Islamia," Indian Express, 20 January.
- [5] Nehru, Jawaharlal (1989) [1946]: *The Discovery of India*, Centenary Edition, New Delhi and Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [6] Saima Saeed (2016): Safeguarding Educational Rights of Minorities. *Economic & Political Weekly EPW* Vol II No. 29. Published on July 16, 2016.
- [7] Shri Mukhtar Abbas Naqvi (2021): Union Minister for Minority Affairs in a written reply in the Rajya Sabha today. Posted On: 06 DEC 2021 3:57 PM by PIB Delhi. NAO/MoMA-RSQ-90. Release ID: 1778480. Read this release in Urdu. www.pib.gov.in/
- [8] Nupur Thapliyal (2024): Aided Minority Institutions Have Absolute Right To Appoint Principals, Teachers; DoE Can Only Prescribe Qualification & Experience: Delhi HC. Published on 31 May 2024 11:15 AM. <https://www.livelaw.in/high-court/delhi-high-court/delhi-high-court-minority-school-appoint-teacher-principal-259283>
- [9] T M A Pai Foundation and Others Vs State of Karnataka and others (2002) Interpretation of and interplay between Article 30(1) and Article 29(2) of the Constitution. 8 SCC 481. Supreme Court of India, Judgment dated October 31, 2002/November 25, 2002. Quorum: B.N. Kirpal, C.J. and G.B. Pattanaik, V.N. Khare, S. Rajendra Babu, S.S.M. Quadri, Ruma Pal, S.N. Variava, K.G. Balakrishnan, P. Venkatarama Reddi, Ashok Bhan, and Dr Arijit Pasayat.
- [10] *St. Stephen's College vs University of Delhi* (1992)
- [11] *Child Modern Madarsa vs Directorate of Education, Govt. of NCT of Delhi* (2024), Govt. of India, National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI) Case No. 407 of 2020. Ordered on 31 Jan 2024.
- [12] *Al-Qulam English School, vs Joint Secretary, Minorities Development Department, Mumbai* (2024): Direction to the director, Govt. of Bharat, National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI) Case No. 89 of 2021 Ordered on 24 Jan 2024.
- [13] National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions (NCMEI): <https://ncmei.gov.in/document-category/judgements-2024/page/8/> Accessed 10 Jul 2025.
- [14] *State of Karnataka vs T.M.A. Pai Foundation* (2002).
- [15] <https://indiankanoon.org/search/?formInput+doctypes:supremecourt,scorders,highcourts>. Accessed on 10 July 2025.
- [16] Government of India (2025): List of Minority Certified Institutions. Govt. of India, Ministry of Education, Department of Higher Education, National Commission for Minority Educational Institutions. Cited 10 July 2025.
- [17] *St. Stephen's College vs University of Delhi*, AIR 1992 SC 1630.
- [18] *Satimbla Sharma vs St. Paul's Senior Secondary School*, (2011) 13 SCC 760.
- [19] *Modern Dental College and Research Centre vs State of Madhya Pradesh*, (2009) 7 SCC 751.
- [20] *T.M.A. Pai Foundation vs State of Karnataka*, AIR 2003 SC 355.
- [21] *P.A. Inamdar vs State of Maharashtra*, 2003 (2) Suppl. SCR 474 = (2003) 6 SCC 697.
- [22] *Christian Medical College Vellore Association vs Union of India*, 2020 SCC Online SC 423.

- [23] Unni Krishnan vs State of A.P., (1993) 1 SCC 645.
- [24] Islamic Academy of Education vs State of Karnataka, AIR 2003 SC 3724.
- [25] Cochin University of Science and Technology vs Thomas Joan, (2008) 8 SCC 82.
- [26] State of Bombay vs Bombay Educational Society, AIR 1954 SC 561.
- [27] D. A. V. College vs State of Punjab, AIR 1971 SC 1731.
- [28] State of Karnataka vs Associated Management of English Medium Primary & Secondary Schools, 2013 SCC Online SC 581.
- [29] Society for Unaided Private Schools of Rajasthan vs Union of India, (2012) 6 SCC 1.
- [30] Para 29 and 47, Pramati Educational and Cultural Trust vs Union of India, 2014 8 SCC 1.
- [31] Munawar Hussain & Anjali Mehrotra (2021): SC of India on minority education Institutions regarding students' admission & Medium of Instruction. <https://www.rsr.in/post/supreme-court-of-india-on-minority-education/>
- [32] Nilima Chandiramani (2016): Judicial Decisions Relating to Minority Educational Institutions: An Overview. Mainstream Weekly. Vol LIV No 45. New Delhi, October 19, 2016. Published on Sunday, 30 October 2016.
- [33] Shri K.P Shukla & Others vs The State of Maharashtra & Others. 1997 Judgment by Bombay High Court. Jan 11, 1997.
- [34] Modern Dental college and research centre & others vs state of Madhya Pradesh and others. Judgment dated May 02, 2016, by the Supreme Court of India, Civil Appellate Jurisdiction, Civil Appeal No. 4060 of 2009.
- [35] Shri K.P. Shukla & Others v. The State of Maharashtra & Others on January 10, 1997.
- [36] All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE) (2024). New Delhi.
- [37] N. Ammad vs Emjay High School (1998) 6 SCC 674.
- [38] Frank Anthony Public School Employees Association vs Union of India (AIR 1987 SC 311)
- [39] St. Xaviers College vs State of Gujarat.
- [40] Islamic Academy of Education vs State of Karnataka (2003) 6 SCC 697.
- [41] Bal Patil vs Union of India (2005)
- [42] Aligarh Muslim University (AMU) Case (2024)
- [43] Azeez Basha v. Union of India (1967)
- [44] Maharashtra Employees of Private Schools (Conditions of Service) Rules, 1981.
- [45] Hemant Kumar Chhotary vs State of Odisha.
- [46] Mohamed Imranullah S (2025): Judiciary must intervene when consituational rights guaranteed to minorities are threatened: Madras High Court Justice N Anand Venkatesh Published March 27, 2025.
- [47] Anwarul Yaqin, 'Determination of Minority Status: The Judicial Approach', (1980) 22 Journal of the Indian Law Institute 538, 553–4.
- [48] P.P. Craig and S.L. Deshpande, 'Rights, Autonomy and Process: Public Interest Litigation in India', (1989) 9(3) Oxford Journal of Legal Studies 356, 372.
- [49] Manoj Kumar Sinha, 'Minority Rights: A Case Study of India', (2005) 12(4) International Journal on Minority and Group Rights 355, 356–9.
- [50] Yaqin, *supra* note 41, 538.

- [51] Ranu Jain, 'Minority Rights in Education: Reflections on Article 30 of the Indian Constitution', (2005) 40(24) *Economic and Political Weekly* 2430, 2431. *See also, dav College, Jalandhar Etc. v. State of Punjab & Ors.* air 1971 sc 1737, where the Supreme Court held that there must be at least one spoken language for the group to be classified as a linguistic minority. *See also, Arya Pratinidhi Sabha v. State of Punjab* air 1958 Pat 359, where the Patna High Court held that Article 30(1) did not apply to religious sects or denominations. *Similarly, in Arya Samaj Education Trust v. The Director of Education, Delhi Administration*, air 1976 Del 207, Delhi High Court clarified that reformist sects within Hinduism could not be seen as a religious minority under Article 30(1). *See generally*, Shailendra Mohan, 'Minority and Majority Linguistic Groups in India: Issues and Problems', (2010–2011) 70/71 *Bulletin of the Deccan College Post-Graduate and Research Institute* 261, 262.
- [52] *Ibid.*
- [53] Ahmad, *supra* note 66, 98–9.
- [54] Ahmad, *supra* note 66, 98–9.
- [55] Holy Cullen, 'Education Rights or Minority Rights', (1993) 7(2) *International Journal of Law and the Family*, Oxford University Press 143, 143–4.
- [56] Jayna Kothari, *supra* note 57, 70.
- [57] *See generally*, Madhav Khosla, 'Making Social Rights Conditional: Lessons from India', (2010) 8(4) *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, Oxford University Press 739, 765.
- [58] Saima Saeed, *supra* note 95, 17.
- [59] *See generally, St. Stephen's College v. State of Gujarat*, AIR 1974 SC 1389.
- [60] Bakshi, *supra* note 108, 583–4.
- [61] *Ibid et al.*
- [62] Virendra Kumar, *supra* note 125, 200.
- [63] Bhatia, *supra* note 32, 253.
- [64] Partha Chatterjee, 'Religious Minorities and the Secular State: Reflections on an Indian Impasse', (1995) 8(1) *Public Culture* 11, 34.
- [65] Dushyant Kishan Kaul (2022): Excessive state intervention in regulating minority educational institutions. An insidious constitutional aberration. *International Journal on minority and group rights*. Volume 30: Issue 1. ISSN: 1571-8115(P) 1385-4879 (O)
- [66] *Shri. Balmukund Rathi Shiksha vs State of Maharashtra*, Thru. Secretary on 5 Dec 2016 declared by the Vasanti A Naik bench.
- [67] *State of Bihar vs Syed Raza* AIR 197 SC 2425.
- [68] *Milli Talimi Mission Bihar and Ors Vs State of Bihar and Ors.* 1984 (4) SCC 500.
- [69] Holly Cullen, 'Education Rights or Minority Rights?', 7(2) *Int. J. Law Policy Family* (1993) pp. 143–177. *See also* D. Beiter, *The Protection of the Right to Education by International Law* (Leiden: Martinus Nijhoff, 2005)
- [70] Julie Ringelheim. *Between Identity Transmission and Equal Opportunities: The Multiple Dimensions of Minorities' Right to Education*. DOI: 10.1163/9789004244740_005

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